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Stress and Coping Strategies among Uniformed Personnel in the Enforcement of Law

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Abstract

This study determined the stress and coping strategies of uniformed law enforcement personnel in the Philippine National Police in Ilocos Sur. It examined their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, rank/position, years in service, and monthly family income.

The study utilized the descriptive research design and a survey questionnaire as the main tools for gathering data. Several statistical tools were used, such as frequency and percentage, weighted mean, t-test, Scheffe test, and ANOVA (Analysis of Variance).

The uniformed personnel were male-dominated young adults in marital relationships, with bachelor's degree holders holding the lowest rank as police officers, earning an average monthly income, and mostly in the service for more than five years. The sources of stress among the uniformed personnel were highest on work-related, followed by peer-related, and lowest on family-related.

The uniformed personnel utilized open communication with their colleagues and resorted to doing exercises to relieve their stress. No significant relationships were noted between the sources of stress among the uniformed personnel and their profile variables. The longer the length of service of the uniformed personnel, the more they encountered work-related stresses. The Proposed program was formulated to be implemented in the PNP Ilocos Sur to minimize workplace stress occurrences.

Keywords: coping strategies, stress, uniformed personnel

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Background of the Study

Both military women and men are exposed to a wide range of stressor events as a part of military training and work assignments. Military women may also experience stressors related to being a woman in a traditionally and predominantly male work environment. Employees who experience a moderate degree of job stress perform their jobs most efficiently, while those who experience either low or high work-related stress show reduced work efficiency. The potential moderating effects of various physiological, psychological, and social factors on the stress-job performance relationship have also been examined; these moderators may act by contributing to or reducing the resources that individuals can bring to bear in coping with stressors. Coping is one of several psychosocial factors posited to moderate or mediate the relationship between stress and job functioning (Bray et al., 2020).

Military personnel are at a high risk of exposure to potentially traumatic events. This makes them an “at-risk group” who are vulnerable to suffering from psychological distress and mental health problems, including depression, family violence, substance abuse, and post-traumatic stress disorder, all of which are problems for military services and a threat to occupational functionality. The impact of mental health on decision-making is especially significant given the high technology, fast-paced warfare of the 21st century, the battlefield which leaves little margin for error. Furthermore, many military forces have to cope with increasingly complicated conflicts with an ever-decreasing number of soldiers available to fulfil these duties. Troops need to function at peak efficiency, and inefficiencies imposed by work stress and mental health problems may have very serious consequences (Langston et al. 2017).

Morgan et al. (2017) found in their study on coping strategies among the military that the most frequently reported coping behaviour was thinking of a plan to solve the problem, followed by talking to a friend, engaging in a hobby, and exercising or playing sports. The least often endorsed coping behaviors were smoking marijuana or using illicit drugs and thinking about hurting or killing oneself, followed by having a drink or lighting up a cigarette. Specifically, talking to a friend, exercising or playing sports, engaging in a hobby, and thinking of a plan were associated with fewer anxiety, perceived stress, and depression symptoms, whereas smoking a cigarette, having a drink, and thinking about hurting or killing oneself were associated with more anxiety, perceived stress, and depressive symptoms.

The constant possibility of encountering traumatic stressors is a persistent concern for individuals who opt for a military career. Beyond stressors directly related to operations, various other job-related pressures profoundly impact the lives of military personnel. Examining the origins of stress and its prevalence within the U.S. military, it was found that 26% of troops reported significant work-related stress. In comparison, an additional 15% experienced considerable emotional distress linked to these stressors. Consequently, the research demonstrated that engaging in combat, facing high casualties, and experiencing unexpected deployments were all associated with heightened levels of psychological distress. Whether stemming from traumatic events or work-related pressures, mental disorders have shown a notable influence on both workforce and retention rates (Langston, 2017).

The study conducted by Hoseini et al. (2023) regarding burnout in the military found the prevalence of high emotional exhaustion, the prevalence of high depersonalization, and

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the prevalence of low personal accomplishment. Work environment factors (such as workload and shift work), psychological factors (anxiety, depression, stress), and duration and quality of sleep were risk factors of burnout or its subscales. Also, psychological distress was observed as a consequence of burnout. It showed a relatively moderate prevalence of burnout. Burnout was associated with factors related to work environment and psychological variables.

Stress can cause a variety of symptoms. Some people experience back pain and tense muscles, headaches, nausea or stomach pain, trouble sleeping and fatigue. Less-obvious symptoms include irritability, anxiety or panic attacks, difficulty making decisions, trouble concentrating, apathy, feelings of being out of control, and changes in behaviour. These stress-management techniques help minimize symptoms: a) **Focus on what you can control**- When you feel stressed out by a situation, think about what you can control. Give yourself some action steps. If your actions will not impact the situation, then learn to accept it for what it is. b). **Exercise**. Commit to a regular workout. Run. Lift. Swim, c). **Make time for your favourite activity**. Treat yourself to some "me" time. Continue doing those activities that give you pleasure. Try to fit leisure activities and hobbies into your day. d). **Simplify your life**. Do whatever you can to simplify your life. Say no to social commitments you don't enjoy, and limit your time on email and social networking sites. e). **Laugh often**. Look for humour in everyday life. Watch your favourite comedy or laugh with a friend. You can take your military duty seriously without taking yourself seriously; f) **Breathe deeply**. By taking long, slow breaths, you increase your oxygen and calm yourself down, g) **Stay in the present**. Try to be aware of what is happening in the present moment and focus on what you are doing at any given moment. When your thoughts turn to the past and the future, gently try to return them to the here and now; h) **Learn how to relax**. Try some visualization exercises, such as picturing yourself in a relaxed or happy setting, like the beach. Go for a walk. Listen to music, and **Get organized**. Too much clutter can add to the feeling things are out of control (Military One source, 2020).

The most widely publicized mental health challenges military members encounter are post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and depression. US service members deployed to Afghanistan and Iraq have been affected by PTSD or depression. Although these mental health concerns are prominently highlighted, it is crucial to acknowledge that other issues, such as suicide, traumatic brain injury (TBI), substance use disorder (SUD), and interpersonal violence, can be equally detrimental. These challenges can have far-reaching consequences, significantly affecting military members and their families. Although combat and deployments are known to be associated with increased risks for these mental health conditions, military service can also give rise to challenges. The presentation of these mental health concerns may not follow a specific timeline. However, there are particularly stressful periods for individuals and families, especially during proximity to combat or transitioning from active military service (Inoue et al., 2023).

Family communication was associated with depression/anxiety. This was a somewhat surprising finding given that effective communication generally contributes substantially to youth's positive development within families. The pattern of results highlights the need to allocate resources, especially when they are limited, to those families grappling with injury-related stressors, those with more and older children, and those managing the burdens associated with multiple deployments of longer length. Programs, interventions, and support services that foster healthy parental social and family functioning, positive

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interactions, and resiliency are critical to minimizing operational stress's impact on the workforce and the family members who support them (Briggs et al., 2020).

Many military families are resilient despite exposure to deployments and other military life challenges, so understanding the potentially buffering role of adaptive family functioning in the face of military operational stress has important implications for developing and disseminating interventions that promote and support resilience. The impact of family communication and family relationship satisfaction are critical dimensions to explore, given that military families often endure changes in roles and leadership, periods with limited communication, physical separation, and a host of stressors related to the process of deployment and reintegration (Saltzman et al., 2011).

A mental health program for all members of the Armed Forces of the Philippines (AFP) is ongoing to prevent stigma on mental health issues among soldiers. Some soldiers are not willing to share their traumatic experiences. The uniformed personnel did not want to tell the story or to tell someone about their traumatic experience, so with this trauma risk management program, they encourage people to speak up and air their experiences. Their mental health program aims to detect which among all military members, including retired soldiers, had traumatic experiences like "armed encounters with threat groups or local terrorist groups (Marquez, 2020).

Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework

The study adopted Hans Selye's stress theory. He theorized that overexposing the body to stress would cause what he called "general adaptation syndrome," which could lead to shock, alarm, and eventually exhaustion. Far from being limited to soldiers, the range of potential sufferers included all of humanity.

Another theory suited for the study is the Transactional theory of stress and coping, developed by Lazarus and Folkman, which has been particularly instrumental in shaping stress and coping. They mentioned stress as an external stimulus, stress as a response, stress as an individual/environmental transaction (Amanda et al. 2017).

The study assessed the stress and coping strategies of uniformed personnel in the enforcement of law. Box number 1 is the Input that dealt with the profile of the respondents, the stress, and coping strategies utilized by the uniformed personnel in the enforcement of the law. Box number 2 is the process that deals with data gathering, interpretation, and analysis. Box number 3 is the Output that focuses on stress management activities to minimize the stress the uniformed personnel encounter.

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Research Paradigm

Statement of the Problem

This study assessed the sources of stress and coping strategies of uniformed personnel in the enforcement of law in PNP Maritime Group, Ilocos Sur MARPSTA assigned at Ilocos Sur.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of their;
 - a. age;
 - b. sex;
 - c. civil status
 - d. highest educational attainment;
 - e. monthly family income;
 - f. rank/position; and
 - g. number of years in service?
2. What are the sources of stress encountered by the uniformed personnel along;

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- a. work-related;
 - b. family; and
 - c. peer related?
3. What are the coping strategies utilized by the uniformed personnel in managing their stress?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the stress encountered by the uniformed personnel across their profile variables?
 4. Is there a significant difference between the stress encountered by the uniformed personnel across their profile variables?
5. Based on the findings, what proposed stress management program can be formulated to minimize the stress encountered by the uniformed personnel?

Null Hypothesis

The study was tested in its null form at 0.05 level of significance that;

1. There is no significant relationship between the stress encountered by the uniformed personnel across their profile variables
- 2.. There is no significant difference between the stress encountered by the uniformed personnel across their profile variables.

Chapter 2

Methodology

This chapter presents the research methodology, which includes discussions on the research design, subjects of the study, sampling scheme, data gathering instruments, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment of data, and tools for data analysis.

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive research method with the questionnaire as a data-gathering tool to assess the sources of stress and the coping strategies among uniformed personnel in managing their stress. According to Best (2015), descriptive research is the process that goes beyond mere gathering and tabulation of data. It involves an element of interpretation of the meaning and the significance of what is described. This description often combines with comparison and contrast involving the measurements, classifications, interpretation, and evaluation.

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Population and Locale of the Study

The study's respondents were the selected uniformed personnel of the PNP Maritime group assigned in Ilocos Sur. The respondents were composed of 50 uniformed personnel who are actively with the service. To represent the population, purposive sampling was used and was delimited to those uniformed personnel present and cooperating during the data gathering. It was conducted on November 11, 2023, at their respective offices.

Data Gathering Tool

The study utilized a survey questionnaire based on previous studies and articles related to the study, particularly in the article by Menestrel and Kizer (2019). Part I focused on the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, monthly family income, rank/position, and number of years in service. Part II tackled the sources of stress and the coping strategies utilized by the uniformed personnel, which were work-related, family-related, and peer-related.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before gathering data, the researcher obtained permission from the Dean of the Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies and the Chief of PNP Maritime Group Ilocos Sur. Following these approvals, the researcher obtained consent from the respondents. Data collection occurred in the second semester of 2023-2024, conducted directly by the researcher. Ethical precautions were meticulously observed throughout the study, ensuring adherence to ethical standards and procedures.

Voluntary participation entails that all research participants are free to choose whether or not to participate in the study without experiencing any form of persuasion or coercion.

Informed consent denotes a scenario where all prospective participants are provided with and comprehends all necessary information to decide their participation. This encompasses details regarding the study's advantages, potential risks, funding sources, and institutional authorization. Top of Form

Confidentiality involves knowing the participants' identities while removing any identifiable details from your report.

All participants have the right to privacy, necessitating the safeguarding of their personal information for the entire duration of its storage or usage. Even in cases where data collection cannot be anonymous, prioritizing confidentiality is crucial whenever feasible.

Treatment of the Data

Frequency and percentage were used for Problem No.1 on the respondent's profile. The frequency was determined based on the number of respondents who answered or checked a particular item on the questionnaire.

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Formula:

$$P = \frac{F \times 100}{N}$$

where: P = percentage

F = frequency

N = total number of respondents

For problem No. 2 on the sources of stress and the coping strategies used by the uniformed personnel, the weighted mean was used. The weighted mean is the mean of a set of values wherein each value or measurement has a different weight or degree of importance. This study used a five-point rating scale system, as shown in the table below.

Formula:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fi}{N}$$

where: \bar{x} = weighted mean

N = total # of population; and

fi = frequencies corresponding to the given items.

A four Likert Scale was used in the analysis.

Point Value	Mean Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Value
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Encountered
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Encountered
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Encountered
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Encountered
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Encountered

Point Value	Mean Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Value
A	4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Utilized
B	3.50 – 4.49	Often	Utilized
C	2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Utilized
D	1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Utilized
E	1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Utilized

Problem No. 3 and 4 on the significant relationships and differences between sources of stress of the uniformed personnel, Analysis of Variance was used to test the difference, whereas Chi-Square was used to test the relationship between variables.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

$$F = \frac{MSb}{MSw}$$

Where:

MSb-Mean Square Between

MSw-Mean Square Within

Chi-Square

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{\quad}$$

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E

Where: O =observed number of cases
 E = (row total) (column total)
 Grand total _____

Chapter 3

Results and Discussions

This chapter presents the findings of the study based on the data gathered from the nurse respondents.

Part 1. Respondent's Profile

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, employment status, and monthly family income.

Age. The majority of the respondents were in the age bracket of 31-40 years old, with a frequency of 24, or 48 percent, followed by 21-30 years old, with a frequency of 20, or 40 percent, 41-50, with a frequency of 4, or 8 percent, and 51 and above with a frequency of 2, or 4 percent. It revealed that the respondents belong to young adults. As cited by Erik Erikson, the respondents belong to the stage of intimacy versus isolation. The ability to be able to open up romantically and emotionally to those closest to the individual. Those with intimacy have strong relationships with others. Isolation is the inability to form close relationships. These individuals are more depressed and lonelier. It is developed by working on being able to share things about yourself with others. Additionally, one must practice listening to others Kimberly Slifer (2023).

Sex. The majority of the uniformed personnel were males, with a frequency of 46, or 92 percent, and females, with a frequency of 4, or 8 percent. It revealed that the respondents were male-dominated. This particular job is undoubtedly for men. However, there are a few women who resort to this job. Some prefer women soldiers in administrative and support functions, citing the physical differences between males and females and how the latter is unnaturally suited to physically demanding tasks in the frontline and combat operations. Likewise, as of 2016, only 4% of the total female commissioned officers are assigned to Naval Forces across the country.

Civil status. The majority of the respondents were married, with a frequency of 38 or 76 percent, followed by singles, with a frequency of 12 or 24 percent. It revealed that the

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respondents were into marital relationships and having their families. It goes to show that the uniformed personnel have the responsibility to support their families and their children.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents in terms of their Profile Variables
n=50

Profile Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age (in years)		
21 – 30	20	40.0
31 – 40	24	48.0
41 – 50	4	8.0
51 an above	2	4.0
Sex		
Male	46	92.0
Female	4	8.0
Civil Status		
Single	12	24.0
Married	38	76.0
Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	50	100.0
Rank/Position		
Patrolman	14	28.0
Police Corporal	14	28.0
Police Staff Sergeant	12	24.0
Police Master Sergeant	4	8.0
Police Senior Master Sergeant	4	8.0
Police Executive Master Sergeant	2	4.0
Monthly Family Income (in Php)		
Below P15,000	12	24.0
15,001-25,000	16	32.0
25,001-35,000	15	30.0
35,001-45,000	3	6.0
45,001 and above	4	8.0
Number of Years in Service		
Below 1 year	3	6.0
1 – 2	10	20.0
3 – 4	7	14.0
5 and above	30	60.0

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Rank/ Position. It showed that most respondents held the position of Patrolman and Police corporal, with a frequency of 14, or 28 percent; Police Staff Sergeant, with a frequency of 12, or 24 percent; Police Master Sergeant, and Police Senior Master Sergeant, with a frequency of 4, or 8 percent, and Police Executive Master Sergeant with a frequency of 2 or 4 percent. It revealed that most uniformed personnel were holding the lowest rank in their stations. In every organization, rank and file personnel are the most in the number of personnel.

Monthly family income. Most respondents earned an income of P15,001-P25,000 with a frequency of 16, or 32 percent, P25,001-P35,000 with a frequency of 15, or 30 percent, below P15,000 with a frequency of 12, or 24 percent, P45,001 and above with a frequency of 4, or 8 percent, and P35,001-P45,000 with a frequency of 3, or 6 percent. It revealed that most respondents earned the average income. The study by Jose Albert, Angelo Santos, and Jana Vizmanos (2018), as cited by Chua, 2020, divides the social classes into poor, low-income but not poor, lower-middle, middle, upper-middle, upper-middle but not rich, and rich. Those earning P15,000-P25,000 are considered low-income but not poor. Also, according to NEDA Director Pernia, a typical Filipino family needs a monthly income of P42,000 to live decently. Roughly P42,000 a month would be a more decent income, at least to live above the poverty line (2018).

Number of years in service. It revealed that the majority of the respondents were in the service for five years and above, with a frequency of 30 or 60 percent, 1-2 years, with a frequency of 10 or 20, 3-4 years, with a frequency of 7, or 14 percent, and below one year with a frequency of 3, or 6 percent. It revealed that most respondents were in the service for a few years since they were still considered young adults and getting their experiences in their field of work. In the police force, the factors contributing to stress can also influence job satisfaction and length of service. (Allisey et al., 2014; Kuo, 2015; Lambert et al., 2017)

Part II. Sources of Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel

The sources of stress encountered by the uniformed personnel were listed in Tables 2 to 4 measuring work-related, family-related, and peer-related.

Table
Sources of Work-Related Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel
n=50

Indicators	Weighted Means	Transmuted Rating
1. Service-related mental health conditions and injuries incurred in the line of duty, military-duty-related deaths	2.10	ME
2. Experience frequent exposure to heavy casualties.	1.68	SE
3. Unexpected deployments to other places	3.18	ME
4. They are required to function within a hostile community, serve as first responders, or be directly exposed to	2.10	SE

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stressful or traumatic experiences that could put them at risk for traumatic stress.

5. Work overload, work-family conflict, and job stress	2.58	ME
6. Organizational factors such as poor policy	1.88	SE
7. Emotional exhaustion and physical fatigue	2.18	SE
8. Environment factors (such as workload, shift work), psychological factors (anxiety, depression, stress), and duration and quality of sleep	2.30	SE
9. Service members are frequently called upon in times of national or international crisis, disaster, or terrorism.	2.48	SE
10. Body handling and other mortuary responsibilities, especially in circumstances that involve exposure to gruesome human remains	1.50	SE
AWM	2.20	SE

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Rating	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Encountered (HE)
3.50 – 4.49	often	Encountered (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Encountered (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Encountered (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Encountered (NE)

As work-related stress, the highest indicators are item numbers 3 and 5, “Unexpected deployments to other places,” and “Work overload, work-family conflict, and job stress,” with a weighted mean of 3.18, and 2.58 or “Moderately Encountered.” It revealed that the respondents were somehow affected and a source of stress when they were assigned to other stations and were overworked in their assignments. This scenario is not new to the uniformed personnel because their job requires relocation when the need arises. Langston (2017) confirmed that being in combat, exposure to heavy casualties, and unexpected deployments all correlated with increased levels of psychological distress among military personnel.

The lowest indicators are items numbers 2 and 10, “Experience frequent exposure to heavy casualties,” and “Body handling and other mortuary responsibilities especially in circumstances that involve exposure to gruesome human remains,” with a weighted mean of 1.50 and 1.68, or “Slightly Encountered.” It implies that the uniformed personnel encountered a little bit stressed when they are with victims of death due to casualties. Stressors related to operations, like danger, unpredictability, and extended duty hours, can be problematic but are also expected (Shane, 2010; Violanti et al., 2017). Despite being detrimental to police personnel, these operational-related pressures must also be anticipated due to the nature of their work.

Overall, the sources of work-related stress encountered by the uniformed personnel got an average weighted mean of 2.20, or “Slightly Encountered.” It revealed that the uniformed personnel lightly encountered work-related stress. This implies that the uniformed personnel had adjusted themselves to different kinds of stressors while on duty. It is part of

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their training and responsibilities, and they were trained in relation to their jobs. Langston et al. (2017) mentioned that military personnel are at a high risk of exposure to potentially traumatic events. This makes them an “at-risk group” who are vulnerable to suffering from psychological distress and mental health problems, including depression, family violence, substance abuse, and post-traumatic stress disorder, all of which are problems for military services and a threat to occupational functionality.

Family-related stress is continually encountered in Table 3.

Table 3

**Sources of Family-Related Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel
n=50**

Indicators	WM	DE	TV
1. I encounter multiple family relocations and separations that lead to transitions in residence, communities, jobs, child care, health care, and schools	1.66		SE
2. Occurrence of duty related illness, injury or even death	1.48		NE
3. moving that affects our families, in times of war, when fathers and mothers deploy to combat zones and are away from loved ones for as much as an entire year.	1.46		NE
4. I encounter problems in intrafamilial relationships, with poorer marital satisfaction, impaired family functioning, and greater family distress and violence	1.56		SE
5. Having physical injury and psychological traumatic stress that complicate a military family's well-being, lead to problems within the family, affect the marital relationships	1.48		NE
6. I experienced impaired family communication, impaired parenting, impaired family organization, and lack of guiding belief systems	1.56		SE
7. perceived lower relationship quality in both service members and their spouses	1.54		SE
8. occurrence of higher rates of distress, depression, suicidal ideation, and poorer adjustment	1.50		SE
9. having burden to family members secondary to combat-related injury includes long and stressful rounds of treatment and rehabilitation and changes in functioning that require family members to assume new roles within the family, such as caregiving.	1.34		NE
10. occurrence of higher rates of depression, parenting and marital strain	1.34		NE
AWM	1.49		NE

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Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Rating
4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Encountered (HE)
3.50 – 4.49	Often	Encountered (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Encountered (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Encountered (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Encountered (NE)

The indicators were rated very low however, the highest indicators are item numbers 1, 4, and 6, "I encounter multiple family relocations and separations that lead to transitions in residence, communities, jobs, child care, health care, and schools," "I encounter problems in intrafamilial relationships, with poorer marital satisfaction, impaired family functioning, and greater family distress and violence," and "I experienced impaired family communication, impaired parenting, impaired family organization, and lack of guiding belief systems," with a weighted mean of 1.56, and 1.66 or "Slightly Encountered." It revealed that the respondents were somewhat affected and stressed when it came to family concerns. If the officers were always working late and missing important family or friend events, it could cause problems between the couple. It would also cause problems if the spouse was at home making dinner waiting for their officer to show up and he/she had to work late. There could likewise be problems if the officer constantly called in a while at a family event, a child's sporting event, or even a date. It causes the spouse and children to feel as if they are not as important as the police officer's job, or it could cause them to be sad or disappointed for always missing their events (Karaffa et al. 2015)

As confirmed by Briggs et al. (2020), there is a need to allocate resources, especially when there are limited, to those families grappling with injury-related stressors, those with more and older children, and those managing the burdens associated with multiple deployments of longer length.

Programs, interventions, and support services that foster healthy parental social and family functioning, positive interactions, and resiliency are critical to minimizing the impact of operational stress on both the workforce and the family members who support them.

The lowest indicators are items numbers 9 and 10, "having burden to family members secondary to combat-related injury includes long and stressful rounds of treatment and rehabilitation and changes in functioning that require family members to assume new roles within the family, such as caregiving," and "occurrence of higher rates of depression, parenting and marital strain," with a weighted mean of 1.34, or "Not Encountered," It implies that the uniformed personnel did not experience stressors related to occurrences of mental and marital problems. As mentioned by Inoue et al. (2023), health concerns are prominently highlighted, such as suicide, traumatic brain injury, substance use disorder, and interpersonal violence, which can be equally detrimental. These challenges affect military members and their families. Combat and deployments are associated with increased risks for these mental health conditions. There are stressful periods for individuals and families, especially during periods of proximity to combat or when transitioning from active military service.

Overall, the sources of family-related stress encountered by the uniformed personnel got an average weighted mean of 1.49, or "Not Encountered." It revealed that the uniformed personnel did not experience family-related stress. This might be related to the

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fact that their families were knowledgeable about the background of work of their uniformed family members.

Table 4
Sources of Peer-Related Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel
n=50

Indicators	WM	TR
1. Having problems in relationships with co-workers.	1.94	SE
2. Having problems in the relationship with the immediate supervisor.	1.86	SE
3. military sexual trauma, including sexual harassment and sexual assault .	1.26	NE
4. peer pressures.	1.92	SE
5. lack of support from co-workers and seniors on designation tasking.	1.88	SE
6. transitioning from the military services.	1.50	SE
7. Encounter disciplinary actions from co-workers.	1.48	NE
8. physical problems such as pain, conflicts with leadership.	1.42	NE
9. reductions in rank.	1.28	NE
10. 10. administrative separation from service.	1.22	NE
	AWM	SE
	1.58	

Legend:

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3.50 – 4.49	Often	Encountered (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Encountered (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Encountered (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Encountered (NE)

The table displayed the sources of peer-related stress encountered by the uniformed personnel.

The indicators were equally rated very low however, the highest indicators are item numbers 1, and 4, "Having problems in relationships with co-workers" and "peer pressures," with a weighted mean of 1.92, and 1.94 or "Slightly Encountered."

This implies that the uniformed personnel did not experience problems or pressure from their colleagues. They are loaded with work, and they just focus on their responsibilities. Marquez (2022) cited that uniformed personnel did not want to tell the story or to tell someone about their traumatic experience, so with this trauma risk management program, they encourage people to speak up and air their experiences. Their mental health program is to detect which among all military members, including retired soldiers, had traumatic experiences like "armed encounter with threat groups or local terrorist groups.

The lowest indicators are items numbers 3 and 10, "military sexual trauma, including sexual harassment and sexual assault," and "administrative separation from service," with a weighted mean of 1.22 and 1.26, or "Not Encountered," It implies that the uniformed personnel did not encounter those kinds of stressors among their peers. It means to say that

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there is a smooth working relationship between them. The Sexual Assault Prevention and Response Office (SAPRO) establishes the broad policy for DoD “guided by five critical focus areas”: prevention, victim assistance, investigation, accountability, and assessment. Prevention is a critical element of the wider policy because it is seen as the means to end sexual violence of any kind and comply with the “zero tolerance” directive given by the Secretary of Defence in 1994 (SAPRO, 2017; VA, 2004).

Overall, the sources of peer-related stress encountered by the uniformed personnel got an average weighted mean of 1.58, or “Slightly Encountered.” It revealed that the uniformed personnel somewhat encountered a little stress when it came to their relations with their colleagues. It is just normal for individuals to have misunderstandings once in a while with their colleagues. It makes relationships stronger and better.

Moreover, Table 5 shows the overall sources of stress encountered by the uniformed personnel.

The indicators were equally rated very low. However, the highest source of stress among the uniformed personnel is on work-related, with a weighted mean of 2.20, or “Slightly Encountered,” followed by peer-related, with a weighted mean of 1.58, or “Slightly Encountered.” It goes to show that uniformed personnel encounter more stress and more work-related. Since they are exposed to the workplace for a longer period and encounter a lot of challenges and problems, it is normal for stressors to be present. Hosseini et al. (2023) found burnout in the military, like the prevalence of high emotional exhaustion, the prevalence of high depersonalization, and the prevalence of low personal accomplishment. Work environment factors (such as workload and shift work), psychological factors (anxiety, depression, stress), and duration and quality of sleep were shown as risk factors for burnout.

Table 5
Summary of Sources of Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel
n=50

Source	WM	TR
Work	2.20	SE
Family	1.49	NE
Peer	1.58	SE
OWM	1.75	SE

Legend:

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3.50 – 4.49	Often	Encountered (E)
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Encountered (ME)
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Encountered (SE)
1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Encountered (NE)

The lowest sources of stress among the uniformed personnel are family-related, with a weighted mean of 1.49, or “Not Encountered.” It implies that the families of uniformed

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personnel are aware of the nature of the work of their uniformed family members. They know that the work of uniformed personnel is different compared to other professions. Lack of support at home can make stress worse, while not taking time off with your friends and family can have similar effects (Cherney, 2018).

Overall, the sources of stress among the uniformed personnel got an overall weighted mean of 1.75, or "Slightly Encountered." As mentioned, the uniformed personnel knew the nature of their work and were used to it since these were part of being a public servant. As mentioned by (Military Source One, 2020), when a person feels stressed out by a situation, think about what you can control. Give yourself some action steps. If your actions have no impact on the situation, learn to accept it for what it is, **exercise**, commit to a regular workout, and **make time for your favourite activity**. Treat yourself to some "me" time and continue doing those activities that give you pleasure.

Part III. Coping Strategies Utilized by Uniformed Personnel in Managing Their Stress

Table 6 shows the coping strategies utilized by the uniformed personnel in managing their stress.

The highest indicators are items numbers 1 and 7, "I establish open communication with others," and "I resort to having exercise to relieve my stress," with a weighted mean of 3.62 and 3.66 or "Utilized." It revealed that the respondents resort to having good working relationships with their colleagues where they communicate openly with one another and thereby use body stretches for good circulation. The findings are similar to the study of Morgan et al. (2017) on the coping strategies among the military in that the most reported coping behaviour was thinking of a plan to solve the problem, followed by talking to a friend, engaging in a hobby, and exercising or playing sports.

The lowest indicators are item numbers 5 and 9, "I set limits appropriately and say no to requests that would create excessive stress in my life," and "I say no to social commitments I do not enjoy, and limit my time on email and social networking sites," with a weighted mean of 3.20, and 3.26, or "Moderately Utilized," It implies that the uniformed personnel decides properly before anything is undertaken. With their busy workload, they seldom resort to social media use. Stress is part of being human, and it can help motivate you to get things done. Even high [stress](#) from serious illness, job loss, a death in the family, or a painful life event can be a natural part of life. You may feel down or anxious, and that's normal too for a while (Medically Reviewed by [Sabrina Felson, MD](#), on September 12, 2023). Users of social media may experience bullying, shaming, and negative responses to their posts. These users may also experience discomfort due to the comparison of their self-image and life satisfaction to other users. Additionally, negative social media behaviours can cause isolation, depression, and mood changes based on negative content users see while scrolling (Belluomini, 2015).

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Table 6

Coping Strategies Utilized by Uniformed Personnel in Managing Their Stress

n=50

Indicators	WM	DE	TV
1. establish open communication with others.	3.62		U
2. I workplace morale by creating opportunities for social interactions	3.58		U
3. I talk my stress out with my friends and significant others	3.42		MU
4. I am assertive instead of aggressive. Asserting my feelings, opinions, or beliefs instead of becoming angry, defensive, or passive	3.36		MU
5. I set limits appropriately and said no to requests that would create excessive stress in my life	3.20		MU
6. I seek out social support and spend enough time with my loved ones	3.48		MU
7. I resort to exercise to relieve my stress	3.66		U
8. I make time for my favourite activity	3.56		U
9. I say no to social commitments I do not enjoy and limit my time on email and social networking sites	3.26		MU
10. I talk with someone who can sometimes help my problems seem smaller and more manageable.	3.60		U
	AWM	3.18	MU

Legend:

Statistical Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Transmuted Value
4.50 – 5.00	Always	Highly Utilized (HU)
3.50 – 4.49	often	Utilized (U)
2.50 – 3.49	Sometimes	Moderately Utilized (MU)
1.50 – 2.49	Seldom	Slightly Utilized (SU)
1.00 – 1.49	Never	Not Utilized (NU)

Overall, the coping strategies of the uniformed personnel in managing stress got an average weighted mean of 3.18, or “Moderately Utilized.” It revealed that the uniformed personnel used different coping strategies in managing their stress. As mentioned by Bray et

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al. (2020), the effects of various physiological, psychological, and social factors on the stress-job performance relationship act by contributing to or reducing the resources that an individual can bear in coping with stressors. Coping is one of several psychosocial factors posited to mediate the relationship between stress and job functioning.

Part IV. ANOVA Showing the Significant Results on the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across their profile variables.

Table 7 shows presents the difference in the stress encountered by uniformed personnel across ages.

Table 7

ANOVA Results showing on the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Age

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Work-Related	Between Groups	.046	3	.015	.045	.987	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.764	46	.343			
	Total	15.810	49				
Family-Related	Between Groups	.423	3	.141	.514	.674	Not Significant
	Within Groups	12.614	46	.274			
	Total	13.037	49				
Peer-Related	Between Groups	.045	3	.015	.076	.973	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.206	46	.200			
	Total	9.251	49				
Overall	Between Groups	.057	3	.019	.107	.956	Not Significant
	Within Groups	8.124	46	.177			
	Total	8.180	49				

The computed F-values with significance values higher than the set .05 level of significance imply that age does not affect the stress encountered by uniformed personnel, be it with work, family, or peer-related. It revealed that regardless of the age of the uniformed personnel, they encounter stress while at work. Nevertheless, police personnel over 30 had higher operational stress than those under 30. Old age significantly contributes to police officers' psychological distress during China's COVID-19 pandemic (Huang et al., 2021). Frontline cops are more likely to face cumulative trauma and persistent systemic conflicts, which increase operational stress as they gain experience. This contradicts (Rajesh et al., 2017), who found that younger officers experience more operational stress. This may be because most of the youngsters are in their first year of police service.

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Stress Encountered by

Uniformed Personnel across Sex

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Table 8 shows the difference in the stress encountered by uniformed personnel across sexes. The computed t-values along work-related, family-related, and peer-related stresses have generated significance values which are higher than the set .05 level of significance.

Table 8

t-Test Results showing the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Sex

Aspect	Sex	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Work-Related	Male	46	2.22	.215	.298	48	.723	.473	Not Significant
	Female	4	2.00						
Family-Related	Male	46	1.51	.182	.270	48	.671	.505	Not Significant
	Female	4	1.33						
Peer-Related	Male	46	1.61	.436	.220	48	1.981	.053	Not Significant
	Female	4	1.18						
Overall	Male	46	1.78	.279	.211	48	1.322	.192	Not Significant
	Female	4	1.50						

This suggests that the null hypothesis must be accepted. Hence, Male and female uniformed personnel experience the same work, family, and peer-related stresses. Cherney (2018) mentioned that everyone experiences occasional stress. Because our lives are increasingly jam-packed with obligations, such as school, work, and raising kids, a stress-free day is impossible. Given all the negative effects long-term stress can have on health, though, it's worth making stress relief a priority. If stress is getting in the way of your health and happiness, talk to your doctor about ways you can help manage it.

t-Test Results on the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Civil Status

Table 9 presents the difference in the stress encountered by uniformed personnel across civil status.

Table 9

t-Test Results showing the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Civil Status

Aspect	Civil Status	n	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Error Difference	df	t-value	Sig	Remarks
Work-Related	Single	12	1.93	-.348	.183	48	-1.900	.063	Not Significant
	Married	38	2.28						
Family-Related	Single	12	1.40	-.121	.172	48	-.705	.484	Not Significant
	Married	38	1.52						

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Peer-Related	Single	12	1.66	.108	.145	48	.750	.457	Not Significant
	Married	38	1.55						
Overall	Single	12	1.66	-.120	.136	48	-.886	.380	Not Significant
	Married	38	1.78						

All the computed t-values generated significance values that were higher than the set .05 level of significance. This indicates that single and married uniformed personnel encounter the same types of stress. As cited by Cherney (2018), women are more likely to experience more physical signs of stress compared to their male counterparts. This does not mean that men do not experience stress. Men are more likely to try to escape from stress and not exhibit any signs than females.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Rank/Position

Table 10 shows the results of the test of difference in the stress encountered by uniformed personnel across rank/position.

Table 10

ANOVA Results show the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Rank/Position

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Work-Related	Between Groups	.805	5	.161	.472	.795	Not Significant
	Within Groups	15.005	44	.341			
	Total	15.810	49				
Family-Related	Between Groups	.632	5	.126	.448	.812	Not Significant
	Within Groups	12.405	44	.282			
	Total	13.037	49				
Peer-Related	Between Groups	.127	5	.025	.123	.987	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.124	44	.207			
	Total	9.251	49				
Overall	Between Groups	.295	5	.059	.329	.893	Not Significant
	Within Groups	7.886	44	.179			
	Total	8.180	49				

The computed F-values generated significance values that were higher than the set .05 level of significance. This implies that uniformed personnel encounter the same work, family, and peer-related stress. Regardless of the rank or position of the uniformed personnel, they experience the same sources of stress. Stress is experienced by any person regardless of

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his profile variables. Amanda et al. (2017) mentioned stress as an external stimulus, stress as a response, and stress as an individual environmental transaction.

ANOVA Results on the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Monthly Family Income

Table 11 reveals the difference in the stress encountered by uniformed personnel across monthly family income.

Table 11

ANOVA Results showing the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Monthly Family Income

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Work-Related	Between Groups	2.140	4	.535	1.761	.153	Not Significant
	Within Groups	13.670	45	.304			
	Total	15.810	49				
Family-Related	Between Groups	.331	4	.083	.293	.881	Not Significant
	Within Groups	12.706	45	.282			
	Total	13.037	49				
Peer-Related	Between Groups	1.176	4	.294	1.638	.181	Not Significant
	Within Groups	8.075	45	.179			
	Total	9.251	49				
Overall	Between Groups	.616	4	.154	.916	.463	Not Significant
	Within Groups	7.564	45	.168			
	Total	8.180	49				

The computed F-values and significance values indicate that the results are not significant. This means that income earned by the respondents does not affect the work, family and peer-related stress that they encounter. Management practices are an important workplace intervention, especially management characteristics such as open communication, supportiveness, approachability and appreciation; these ranked the highest in terms of perceived effectiveness. Improving management practices as an intervention and introducing flexibility in working structures were much more apparent in the public sector than in the private sector and in NGOs. Content analysis suggested that there may be a relationship between reported causes of stress and individual and organizational interventions Stranks (2015).

Table 12 provides the difference in the stress encountered by uniformed personnel across several years in service. Data show that the results are not significant.

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Table 12

ANOVA Results show the Difference in the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel across Number of Years in Service

Aspect	Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F-value	Sig	Remarks
Work-Related	Between Groups	2.355	3	.785	2.684	.058	Not Significant
	Within Groups	13.454	46	.292			
	Total	15.810	49				
Family-Related	Between Groups	.513	3	.171	.628	.601	Not Significant
	Within Groups	12.524	46	.272			
	Total	13.037	49				
Peer-Related	Between Groups	.207	3	.069	.351	.789	Not Significant
	Within Groups	9.044	46	.197			
	Total	9.251	49				
Overall	Between Groups	.591	3	.197	1.195	.322	Not Significant
	Within Groups	7.589	46	.165			
	Total	8.180	49				

This is shown in the computed F-values, which generate significance values that are higher than the set .05 level of significance. This means that the length of service of the respondents as uniformed personnel does not affect the type of stress they encountered. Diana and John (2016) found that age and length of service significantly affected police stress in the Chennai Police Commissionerate, India.

Part V. Relationship Between the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel and their Profile Variables

Lastly, Table 10 indicates the relationship between the stress encountered by uniformed personnel.

Table 13
Relationship Between the Stress Encountered by Uniformed Personnel and their Profile Variables

Profile Variable	Work-Related		Family-Related		Peer-Related	
	r-value	sig	r-value	sig	r-value	sig
Age	.032	.828	.062	.670	-.048	.741
Sex	-.104	.473	-.096	.505	-.275	.053
Civil Status	.264	.063	.101	.484	-.108	.457

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Rank/Position	-.044	.763	.019	.896	-.038	.793
Monthly Family Income	-.193	.178	-.028	.845	-.056	.697
Number of Years in Service	.367*	.009	.172	.232	.078	.592

***Significant at .05 level**

Only work-related stress has shown a significant relationship with several years in service. The significant positive relationship implies that the longer the length of service of the uniformed personnel, the more that they encounter work-related stresses.

Meanwhile, there exists no significant relationship between work, family, and peer-related stresses encountered by the respondents and the rest of their profile variables. Hence,

Null Hypothesis

Part VI.

Objectives: To minimize the stressors encountered by the uniformed personnel

Work-Related

a). Unexpected deployments to other places	b). Work overload, work-family conflict, and job stress
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Conducting debriefing sessions after critical incidents to help personnel process their experiences and emotions. ➤ Offering confidential counseling and support services for personnel and their families to address. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Offering workshops on stress management techniques such as mindfulness, relaxation exercises, and time management skills. ➤ Providing training to enhance resilience skills, including problem-solving, positive thinking, and emotional regulation. ➤ Conduct a schedule of activities following the Offering of workshops on stress management techniques such as mindfulness, relaxation exercises, and time management skills. ➤ Implementing flexible work schedules or telecommuting options to help alleviate work-life balance stressors.

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Providing access to counseling services specifically tailored to address family-related stressors, including deployment-related issues, communication challenges, and adjustment difficulties.
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Family-Related

<p>a). encounter multiple family relocations and separations that lead to transitions in residence, communities, jobs, child care, health care, and schools</p>	<p>b). encounter problems in intrafamilial relationships, with poorer marital satisfaction, impaired family functioning, and greater family distress and violence</p>	<p>c). experienced impaired family communication, impaired parenting, impaired family organization, and lack of guiding belief systems</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Establishing support groups for families of uniformed personnel, where they can connect with others facing similar challenges, share experiences, and receive support. ➤ Offering workshops and resources to support parents in managing the unique demands of military life, including parenting during deployments, dealing with separation anxiety, and maintaining family routines. ➤ Partnering with local community organizations and resources to provide additional support and assistance to military families, including childcare 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Offering programs and resources specifically designed to support the emotional well-being of children and adolescents in military families, including counseling services, peer support groups, and educational workshops. ➤ Providing couples therapy or relationship counseling to help military couples strengthen their relationships, improve communication, and navigate the challenges of deployment and reintegration. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Offering resilience training programs for families to help them develop coping skills, strengthen family bonds, and navigate transitions and challenges more effectively. ➤ Implementing programs focused on promoting family well-being, preventing family violence, and providing support and resources to families in crisis.

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services, educational programs, and recreational activities.		
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Peer-Related

a). Having problems in relationships with co-workers	b). peer pressures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Introducing mindfulness and meditation practices to promote relaxation and stress reduction. ➤ Providing training in conflict resolution and communication skills to help personnel navigate interpersonal conflicts effectively. ➤ Organizing team-building exercises and activities to foster a sense of camaraderie, collaboration, and mutual respect among peers. ➤ Pairing personnel with a designated buddy or mentor who can offer support, encouragement, and assistance in navigating work-related challenges. ➤ Providing training and education on diversity, equity, and inclusion to promote a culture of respect, understanding, and acceptance among peers from diverse backgrounds 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Establishing peer support networks where personnel can share experiences and coping strategies with colleagues who understand their unique challenges. ➤ Establishing peer support networks where personnel can openly discuss challenges, share experiences, and provide mutual support. ➤ Implementing peer mentoring programs where more experienced personnel provide guidance, advice, and support to newer members of the team. ➤ Offering training in effective communication skills to help personnel better express themselves, listen actively, and resolve conflicts constructively with their peers

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Chapter 4 Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the findings of the study.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following are the results of this conclusion.

The uniformed personnel were young adults, male-dominated, in marital relationships, Bachelor's degree holders, mostly holding the lowest rank in the military, and mostly in the service for more than five years.

The sources of stress among the uniformed personnel are highest on work-related, followed by peer-related and lowest on family-related.

The uniformed personnel utilized open communication with their colleagues and resorted to exercises to relieve their stress.

No significant relationships were noted between the sources of stress among the uniformed personnel and their profile variables.

The longer the length of service of the uniformed personnel, the more they encounter work-related stresses.

The proposed program is formulated to minimize the sources of their stress.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions provided, the following are at this moment recommended:

The uniformed personnel must continue to perform well in their jobs to be promoted to the next rank, thereby increasing their compensation for their family.

The uniformed personnel must understand and accept the nature of their job to minimize **work-related stress**.

8+8+8 Rule habit: Divide your day into 8+8+8 hours to make a good balance sheet of your life. Eight hours of honest hard work, 8 hours of good sleep, and 8 hours should be spent on (3fs family, friends, and faith. 3hs are health, hygiene, and hobbies, and 2Ss are service and smile.

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To help personnel relax and manage stress, encourage practices such as mindfulness meditation, deep breathing exercises, progressive muscle relaxation, or visualization.

Promote regular physical exercise to reduce stress, improve mood, and increase resilience. This could include group workouts, sports activities, or individual fitness routines.

Emphasize the importance of maintaining a balanced diet, getting adequate sleep, and avoiding excessive alcohol consumption or substance use, as these factors can significantly impact stress levels and overall well-being.

Provide training in time management techniques to help personnel prioritize tasks, set realistic goals, and effectively manage their workload, which can reduce feelings of overwhelm and stress.

Foster a supportive environment where personnel feel comfortable seeking help and support from colleagues, friends, family members, and mental health professionals when needed.

Encourage open and honest communication among team members and leaders, providing opportunities for personnel to express concerns, seek advice, and constructively receive feedback.

Offer resilience-building programs and workshops to help personnel develop coping skills, adaptability, and optimism in the face of adversity.

Establish peer support networks or buddy systems where personnel can connect with others who understand their experiences and provide mutual support during challenging times.

Teach cognitive-behavioral strategies such as cognitive restructuring, problem-solving skills, and positive self-talk to help personnel challenge negative thoughts, manage stressors, and improve their resilience.

Ensure that personnel have access to confidential mental health services, including counselling, therapy, and crisis intervention, as well as resources for addressing mental health concerns such as depression, anxiety, PTSD, or substance abuse.

They must attend wellness programs to relieve themselves of their different types of stress.

The proposed program will be endorsed for adoption in different PNP stations.

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They must have open forum sessions while drinking coffee (kape tayo) and discussing work-related issues and concerns to establish trust and accomplish the work SMART.

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